

The Primary Electroviscous Effect in Surfactant Free Polystyrene Lattices. II. The Effect of increasing Concentrations of Quaternary Ammonium Counterions of different Ionic Sizes

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The primary electroviscous effect and ζ potentials in two different polystyrene lattices of different particle sizes, prepared without the addition of surfactants, have been measured in presence of increasing concentrations of quaternary ammonium counterions of different ionic sizes. It has been found that whereas for the smaller particle size latex the measured electrical contribution to the primary electroviscous effect $(\eta_{el}/\eta_0\phi = [(\eta-\eta_0)/\eta_0\phi] - 2.5)$ increases slowly with increasing counterion concentration due possibly to the simultaneous occurrence of a slow feeble agglomeration of the latex particles, it decreases slowly in the case of the larger particle size latex as required by the theory. The electrophoretically measured ζ potentials (Wiersema-Loeb-Overbeek) as also the surface charge densities (Loeb-Wiersema-Overbeek) show a steady decrease with increasing counterion concentration.

In an earlier communication¹ we have reported the results of viscosity measurements on polystyrene lattices of increasing particle size, prepared in two different series (A and B) without addition of surfactants, in presence of quaternary ammonium counterions of different ionic sizes. The experiments with the A series of lattices were carried out at two different temperatures : A1 at 30°, and A2 and A3 at 35°. The results of two other sets of experiments with the A series of lattices were not reported therein as these pertained to somewhat different experimental temperature : A1 in presence of $(C_4H_9)_4N^+$ at 35°, and A3 with $(C_2H_5)_4N^+$ at 32°. However, since the results from these two sets of experiments are found to generally agree with, and thus confirm the earlier findings, we therefore report below the said results briefly.

Results and Discussion

The electronmicrographs of the polystyrene lattices are shown in Fig. 1^ψ.

The experimental results together with the values

of the significant quantities ΔK_{expt} , $\Delta K(\sigma^W)_{\text{theor}}$, ζ^{WLO} (Ref. 2) and σ^{WLO} (Ref. 3) are recorded in Table 1 for the two lattices of series A (A1: Bu_4NI and A3 : Et_4NBr), and also shown plotted in Fig. 2.

It has been shown¹, after taking into consideration the accuracy of measurement of relative densities, the times of flow in the viscometer and the particle volume fractions, that the quantity $\Delta K_{\text{expt}} = [(\eta-\eta_0)/\eta_0\phi]-2.5$ is accurate to $\pm 5\%$. Similarly, considering the accuracy of the $Z\sigma^{\text{WLO}}$ values ($\pm 2\%$), the $Z(\kappa a)$ interpolation and the lack of knowledge to better precision of the Einstein coefficient (2.5), the calculated quantity ΔK_{theor} has an overall accuracy of $\pm 5\%$.

The measured ζ potentials (all values negative) decreased steadily with increase of added counterion concentration in case of both the lattices. The observed decrease can be described by means of a suitable isotherm for the adsorption of counterions on the charged latex surface. If $\Delta\sigma$ be the decrease in charge density in the Stern plane due to the adsorption at the concentration c (mmol dm^{-3}) of

^ψCourtesy of the Geological Survey of India Laboratory, Calcutta

Fig. 1. Electronmicrographs of polystyrene lattices : (Left) latex A1 ($a = 0.1265 \mu\text{m}$) and (right) latex A3 ($a = 0.667 \mu\text{m}$).

some strongly adsorbed counterion of charge Ze , then it can be shown⁴ that under some plausible assumption

$$\frac{\Delta\sigma}{c} = k_1 - k_2 \Delta\sigma \quad (1)$$

where k_1 and k_2 (related to the electrochemical free energy of adsorption $\Delta\bar{G}$) are constants. The linear plots for the two systems are shown in Fig. 3, and the values of the constants (k_1 and

k_2) together with those of $k_1/k_2 (=zeN_1$; N_1 is the number of adsorption sites per square centimeter) and $\Delta\bar{G}$ are shown in Table 2.

As mentioned earlier¹, the validity of the theoretical value ($= 2.5$) of the Einstein coefficient for suspensions of uncharged spherical particles has been demonstrated in the case of polystyrene lattices by Gillespie⁵, and Stone-Masui and Wattillon⁶. We assume the above result to be valid in the case

TABLE I

Electrolyte concn. $\times 10^3 N$	q^*	κa	$10^4 \lambda \Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$	$\rho_{\text{latex-electrolyte}} (\pm 0.0001) \text{g}^{-1} \text{ml}$	$\eta_{\text{latex-electrolyte}} (\pm 0.0002) \text{cP}$	$\eta_e/\eta_{0\phi} (\Delta K)_{\text{expt}} (\pm 5\%)$	$10^4 -(u/l) (\pm 0.05) \text{cm}^2 \text{s}^{-1} \text{v}^{-1}$	$-\zeta_{\text{WLO}} (\pm 1\%) \text{mV}$	$\sigma^{(w)} (\pm 2\%) \mu\text{C cm}^{-2}$	$10^6 Z e^{(w)} (\pm 2\%) \text{esu}$	$\eta_e/\eta_{0\phi} (\Delta K(\sigma^{(w)})_{\text{theor}})$	$\Delta\sigma \mu\text{C cm}^{-2}$	$10^{-2} (\Delta\sigma/c) \frac{\mu\text{C}}{\text{cm}^2} \frac{\text{dm}^3}{\text{mol}}$
Latex A1													
Added electrolyte : Bu_4NI , temp. = $35 \pm 0.005^\circ$, $\phi = 3.58 \times 10^{-3}$, $a = 0.1265 \mu\text{m}$, residual electrolyte (KCl) = $1.80 \times 10^{-4} N$, $n = 4.0 \times 10^{11}/\text{ml}$													
0.00	3.33	5.65	0.337	0.9943	0.7261	0.1	3.59	62.7	0.28	1.69	0.17	-	-
0.12	5.24	7.34	0.463	0.9940	0.7284	1.0	3.09	47.0	0.24	1.44	0.12	0.042	3.39
0.22	5.90	8.41	0.570	0.9941	0.7309	2.0	2.76	40.5	0.22	1.33	0.08	0.06	2.75
0.32	6.34	9.46	0.695	0.9941	0.7301	1.6	2.51	36.6	0.21	1.26	0.06	0.072	2.22
0.44	6.65	10.5	0.824	0.9940	0.7304	1.8	2.03	28.7	0.18	1.11	0.04	0.096	2.19
Latex A3													
Added electrolyte : Et_4NBr , temp. = $32 \pm 0.005^\circ$, $\phi = 8.90 \times 10^{-3}$, $a = 0.667 \mu\text{m}$, residual electrolyte (KCl) = $2.30 \times 10^{-3} N$, $n = 6.70 \times 10^9/\text{ml}$													
0.00	3.31	106	3.71	0.9958	0.7858	0.6	7.39	96.7	1.90	319	0.02	-	-
3.33	4.55	165	7.74	0.9959	0.7878	0.8	5.86	73.2	1.80	303	0.00	0.10	0.3
5.11	4.75	190	9.62	0.9958	0.7884	0.9	5.39	62.7	1.66	278	0.00	0.24	0.48
7.11	4.89	214	11.6	0.9957	0.7877	0.8	5.07	58.8	1.70	285	0.00	0.20	0.28
9.61	5.00	240	13.4	0.9960	0.7861	0.6	4.73	52.3	1.65	278	0.00	0.25	0.26

Fig. 2. Experimentally measured (ΔK_{expt}) and theoretically calculated [$\Delta K(\sigma^W)_{\text{theor}}$] primary electroviscous effect contributions ($\eta_{\text{cl}}/\eta_0\phi$) and ζ potentials for latex A1 and A3 as function of the added counterion concentration; experimental: (O) A1 (Bu_4N^+), (\bullet) A3 (Et_4N^+); theoretical: lower sets of curves without symbols.

of our suspensions also, which may be justified post-facto on the basis of the finding that the magnitude of the quantity $(\eta - \eta_0)/\eta_0\phi$ marginally exceeds the value 2.5 in every case, the slight excess being attributed to the primary electroviscous effect contribution. Further, the Newtonian behaviour of the polystyrene lattices has been demonstrated by Stone-Masui and Wattillon⁶. Also, the absence of any higher order electroviscous effects in our dilute suspensions can also be legitimately assumed¹.

The results (Table 1) show that the agreement between the experimental and theoretical values of ΔK is good for pure latex A1 (0.1 and 0.17), and less so for pure latex A3 (0.6 and 0.02). On addition of increasing amounts of counterions the trends of variation of ΔK_{expt} and ΔK_{theor} with

Fig. 3. Plots of $\Delta\sigma/c$ vs $\Delta\sigma$ for lattices A1 (Bu_4N^+) and A3 (Et_4N^+).

increasing κa are seen to be (i) sharply opposite for the small particle size latex A1 (ΔK_{expt} increases, ΔK_{theor} decreases), and (ii) somewhat less different for the large particle size latex A3 (ΔK_{expt} decreases after a slight initial increase, whereas ΔK_{theor} also decreases to zero). A similar difference in the trend of variation of ΔK_{expt} and ΔK_{theor} with increasing κa , in the cases of small and large particle size lattices, had been reported by us earlier¹, as also by Stone-Masui and Wattillon⁶.

In order to understand this difference in behaviour, the stability property of the lattices and latex-electrolyte mixtures has to be considered. The repulsive, attractive and total interaction energies for the system have been calculated according to the DLVO theory⁷ using appropriate expressions for the repulsive (V_R) and attractive (V_A) potentials for both (i) small and (ii) large separations between the particles. The surface potentials (Ψ_0) have been approximated by the measured electrokinetic potential ζ , (Hamaker

TABLE 2—ADSORPTION PARAMETERS CALCULATED FROM THE $\Delta\sigma/c$ vs $\Delta\sigma$ PLOTS

Temp. °C	Latex	Quaternary ammonium counterions	$\times 10^{-2} k_1$ $\left(\frac{\mu\text{C}}{\text{cm}^2} \times \frac{\text{dm}^3}{\text{mol}}\right)$	$\times 10^{-2} k_2$ ($\text{dm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1}$)	$\theta = k_1/k_2$ ($\mu\text{C cm}^{-2}$)	$-\Delta G$ (kcal mol^{-1})
35	A1	Bu_4N^+	4.5	29.0	0.16	4.5
32	A3	Et_4N^+	1.3	21.9	0.06	7.1

Fig. 4. The total potential energy of interaction between two spherical particles of polystyrene latex A1 for increasing concentrations of Bu₄NI, as a function of the interparticle separation H (Å); (1) pure latex, $\kappa = 4.5 \times 10^5 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, $\zeta = 62.7 \text{ mV}$, (2) $c = 0.12 \times 10^{-3} \text{ N}$, $\kappa = 5.8 \times 10^5 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, $\zeta = 47.0 \text{ mV}$, (3) $c = 0.22 \times 10^{-3} \text{ N}$, $\kappa = 6.65 \times 10^5 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, $\zeta = 40.5 \text{ mV}$, (4) $c = 0.32 \times 10^{-3} \text{ N}$, $\kappa = 7.48 \times 10^5 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, $\zeta = 36.6 \text{ mV}$ and (5) $c = 0.44 \times 10^{-3} \text{ N}$, $\kappa = 8.3 \times 10^5 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, $\zeta = 28.7 \text{ mV}$; Particle radius $a = 0.1265 \text{ }\mu\text{m}$, Hamaker constant $A = 0.55 \times 10^{-13} \text{ erg}$, $\epsilon = 74.8$, temp. = 35° .

Fig.5. Same as Fig.4 for latex A3 with increasing concentrations of Et₄NBr : (1) pure latex, $\kappa = 15.9 \times 10^5 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, $\zeta = 96.7 \text{ mV}$, (2) $c = 3.33 \times 10^{-3} \text{ N}$, $\kappa = 24.74 \times 10^5 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, $\zeta = 73.2 \text{ mV}$; (3) $c = 5.11 \times 10^{-3} \text{ N}$, $\kappa = 28.49 \times 10^5 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, $\zeta = 62.7 \text{ mV}$, (4) $c = 7.11 \times 10^{-3} \text{ N}$, $\kappa = 32.08 \times 10^5 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, $\zeta = 58.8 \text{ mV}$ and (5) $c = 9.61 \times 10^{-3} \text{ N}$, $\kappa = 35.98 \times 10^5 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, $\zeta = 52.3 \text{ mV}$; particle radius $a = 0.667 \text{ }\mu\text{m}$; Hamaker constant $A = 0.55 \times 10^{-13} \text{ erg}$, $\epsilon = 76$, temp. = 32° .

constant for polystyrene = $0.55 \times 10^{-13} \text{ erg}^8$). The total interaction energy (V_T) for the two different lattices and the corresponding latex-electrolyte mixtures were plotted as a function of the interparticle separation $H(\text{Å})$ (Figs. 4 and 5). It is found that (i) in the case of the pure lattices, the height of the primary maximum is lower for the small particle size latex A1 (300 kT) compared to that for the large particle latex A3 (3100 kT). With increasing concentration of added electrolyte, the maximum comes down significantly due primarily to decreasing surface potential. For the latex A1 the maximum is reduced to much lower values (~55 kT) compared to that in the case of latex A3 (~800 kT), for the highest added electrolyte concentration in both the cases (ζ reduced to 29 mV for A1, and 52 mV for A3). However, the height of the maximum is still great enough to prevent flocculation occurring in the primary minimum region. (ii) In every case a secondary minimum is found to be located at large enough separations

(at ~1400–2200 Å for A1, and ~250–625 Å for A3). The depth of the secondary minimum is, however, found to be rather small, showing in every case a gradual slight increase (upto ~ -4 and ~-0.5 kT respectively) with increasing counterion concentration.

In the present study the experimental conditions had deliberately been so chosen that the possibility of occurrence of coagulation in the region of the 'primary potential energy minimum' was effectively checked. However, as the potential energy diagrams show, there remained the possibility of a loose, almost imperceptible, clustering of the latex particles (somewhat in the nature of an incipient slow orthokinetic flocculation) in the region of the 'secondary potential energy minimum'. The potential energy curves further show that this effect would be the more favoured the higher the added electrolyte concentration and the smaller the particle size. A similar occurrence of flocculation in the region of the

secondary minimum has been reported by other authors also⁹. We are inclined to attribute the anomalous (primary) electroviscous behaviour of the small particle size lattices with increasing counterion concentration to this effect.

In brief, what is implied is this : that during the shear flow of the suspension the mutually closely approaching latex particles tend, while still at finite separation from one another (one to one-and-half times the particle radii, for the similar particle size latex), to get loosely entrapped, very feebly and reversibly, in a very shallow potential trough, and that this tendency increases with increasing added counterion concentration and decreasing particle size. The very slight extra dissipation of energy required to force smooth flow of the particles past one another shows up in a very slightly higher viscosity of the suspension, further increasing with increasing added electrolyte concentration, of the same order of magnitude as (and swamping) the otherwise expected second order electrical double layer interaction generated gradual decrement of viscosity (the Newtonian behaviour of the lattices being not measurably affected)⁶.

The large particale size latex A3 being relatively less susceptible to this confounding effect, shows the normal electroviscosity decrement over the later range of added counterion concentration. So also does the small particle size latex A1 in the pure state, i.e. without counterion addition.

Experimental

The preparation of the lattices, their purification, and their characterisation by way of particle size and solid volume fraction measurements have all been reported earlier¹. The details of experimental measurements of viscosity coefficient η (accuracy $\sim \pm 0.025\%$) and electrophoretic mobility (accuracy $\sim \pm 1\%$) have also been described earlier. The ζ potentials were calculated by the computational method of Wiersema-Loeb-Overbeek² (accuracy of $\zeta^{W.L.O.} \sim \pm 1\%$) and the surface charge densities σ in the diffuse part of the double layer, by using the

computational method of Loeb-Wiersema-Overbeek³ (accuracy of $\sigma^W : \pm 2\%$).

Calculations :

The colloid chemically significant viscosity increment due to electrical interactions in the double layer (the primary electroviscous effect)

$$\Delta K_{\text{expt}} (= K - 2.5) = \left(\frac{\eta - \eta_0}{\eta_0 \phi} \right)_{\phi \rightarrow 0}$$

is given according to the Booth theoretical equation¹⁰ by

$$\Delta K (\sigma^W)_{\text{theor}} = 2.5 q^* \left(\frac{Ze^2}{\epsilon akT} \right)^2 Z(\kappa a) \quad (3)$$

where

$$q^* = (\epsilon kT \sum_{i=1}^s n_i z_i^2 \omega_i^{-1}) / (n_0 e \sum_{i=1}^s n_i z_i^2) \quad (4)$$

and $Z(\kappa a)$ is a known though complicated function of κa , κ the Debye-Hückel parameter, a the radius of the spherical particle of charge Ze , ω_i the ionic mobility of the i -th ions of valence z_i and number density n_i , ϵ and η_0 are the dielectric constant and viscosity of the medium respectively, k is the Boltzmann constant, and T the absolute temperature. It had also been mentioned¹ that since the lattices were of sufficiently small particle volume fraction ϕ and the κa value not too small even in the case of the small particle size latex A1 (lowest κa value > 5) therefore, the need for viscosity measurements at different volume fractions f followed by extrapolation to $\phi \rightarrow 0$ is logically obviated, and that viscosity measurements with a single latex of sufficiently low ϕ value in presence of gradually increasing concentrations of counterions should suffice.

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